

COMPUTER SIMULATION OF HYDROGEN (H₂) ENERGY FUELS CELL TECHNOLOGY ADOPTION FOR ELECTRICITY-POWER GENERATION IN THE COASTAL REGION OF ONDO STATE

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Abstract

Nigeria's coastal regions, including Ondo State, experience severe electricity deficits due to unreliable grid infrastructure and dependence on fossil fuels. This study investigates the adoption of hydrogen (H₂) fuel cell technology as a clean and scalable alternative for power generation in these areas. Using simulations developed in Python and MATLAB, hydrogen fuel cell performance was modeled under varying flow rates (25–50 L/h) and environmental conditions. Results show a linear increase in power output (13.9–27.9 kW) with stable conversion efficiency (approximately 60%), indicating reliability and scalability for rural and industrial applications. Comparative analysis suggests hydrogen fuel cells can reduce greenhouse gas emissions, operational costs, and environmental degradation compared to diesel-powered systems. Techno-economic and policy assessments highlight long-term cost savings, energy security, and social benefits when integrated with solar-powered hydrogen production. The study concludes that hydrogen fuel cells offer a viable, sustainable pathway for clean electricity generation and energy transition in Ondo State's coastal regions.

Keywords

Hydrogen fuel cell,
Renewable energy,
Simulation modeling,
Coastal Ondo State,
Sustainable power
generation

1. INTRODUCTION

Nigeria's national electricity grid remains unreliable and severely constrained, especially in rural and coastal regions. As of 2022, only about 27% of the rural population had access to grid-connected electricity, and the figure has shown little improvement as of November 2024 [1,2]. Coastal and riverine communities in Delta and Ondo States are largely off-grid, depending primarily on diesel generators and biomass energy sources [3,4]. These systems are not only economically inefficient but also environmentally damaging, leading to high greenhouse gas emissions, noise pollution, and health risks.

Despite these challenges, these areas possess vast renewable energy resources, particularly solar and wind that remain underutilized due to inadequate infrastructure and investment in decentralized power systems. A previous hybrid power simulation in Oke Eda, Akure (Ondo State), using HOMER and MATLAB, integrated solar PV, diesel generators, and battery storage to manage extended power outages (~20 hours/day) [5,6]. Although this hybrid model demonstrated cost-effectiveness and technical feasibility as a short-term measure, the reliance on diesel components continues to pose sustainability challenges.

In light of Nigeria's commitment to clean energy transition, hydrogen (H₂) fuel cell technology has emerged as a promising alternative for decentralized, emission-free electricity generation. Hydrogen fuel cells generate power through electrochemical reactions, producing only water and heat as by-products. When combined with renewable energy sources such as solar and wind, hydrogen can serve as a clean, scalable, and sustainable energy carrier.

While several studies have analyzed hybrid solar-diesel systems and renewable hydrogen adoption in other regions of Nigeria, there is no direct simulation or techno-economic feasibility analysis of hydrogen fuel cell-based electricity

systems in Ondo State's coastal region. Existing studies either focus on Northern and Central Nigeria or conduct generic national-level modeling without local environmental or resource considerations. Consequently, there remains a significant research gap in evaluating hydrogen fuel cell adoption tailored to coastal energy demands, renewable potential, and environmental conditions in Ondo State. This study aims to: develop a computer-based simulation model for hydrogen fuel cell systems suitable for electricity generation in coastal Ondo State; analyze the technical performance and efficiency of hydrogen fuel cells under varying environmental and operational parameters; compare hydrogen-based systems with conventional diesel power in terms of cost, energy reliability, and environmental impact; assess the techno-economic feasibility of integrating hydrogen fuel cells with renewable energy sources such as solar and wind; and provide policy recommendations to support hydrogen energy adoption in Nigeria's coastal energy transition framework.

2. RELATED WORK

Hybrid and renewable energy modeling has been widely explored in Nigeria to address the shortcomings of the national grid. For instance, a simulation study in Oke Eda, Akure, integrated solar PV, diesel generators, and battery storage using HOMER and MATLAB to assess cost optimization and energy reliability [5,6]. The results demonstrated that hybrid microgrids could serve as interim solutions before full deployment of cleaner technologies. Recent modeling using the Open Energy Modeling Framework (OEMOF) examined distributed green hydrogen adoption across five electricity distribution companies (DisCos) in Northern and Central Nigeria, projecting an 8% reduction in electricity costs and significant emission reductions by 2060 [7–11a, 11b]. Similarly, a case study in Owerri, Imo State, simulated a proton exchange membrane (PEM) electrolyzer integrated with solar and wind energy sources, achieving continuous hydrogen production under fluctuating weather conditions [12]. These studies highlight hydrogen's potential but remain geographically limited outside the southwestern coastal context.

At the continental level, multidisciplinary research has mapped green hydrogen cost potential across Sub-Saharan Africa, incorporating parameters such as renewable resource availability, groundwater accessibility, and socio-economic readiness [13]. While informative, these continental models lack regional specificity for Nigeria's coastal ecosystems. Moreover, global financial and technical barriers, such as high capital costs, limited public awareness, and inadequate policy support continue to hinder hydrogen development in the country [14–16].

From an environmental standpoint, conventional energy sources like diesel and natural gas have severe ecological and health impacts. Diesel generators are major contributors to greenhouse gas emissions, noise pollution, and air quality deterioration [19–23]. They also increase the risk of cardiovascular and respiratory diseases among local populations [24]. Natural gas, though less polluting, remains associated with methane emissions and widespread gas flaring, particularly in Nigeria's oil-producing regions [22–25]. In contrast, hydrogen fuel cells offer near-zero emissions, higher efficiency, and energy security, especially when powered by renewables [24–25]. Recent literature demonstrates hydrogen production simulations using solar and wind energy in Nigeria's coastal regions, including Ondo State, indicating potential for cleaner energy generation [25]. However, these studies rarely integrate localized hydrogen fuel cell performance modeling, system optimization, or techno-economic evaluation specific to coastal conditions, representing a gap this study directly addresses.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Modeling Framework

This study employed a computational modeling framework to simulate and evaluate the performance of hydrogen fuel cell (HFC) systems for decentralized electricity generation in the coastal region of Ondo State, Nigeria. The model integrates thermodynamic equations, empirical correlations, and simulation parameters to estimate system efficiency and power output under varying hydrogen flow rates, temperature, and humidity conditions. MATLAB and Python environments were used for algorithmic implementation and parametric simulation, respectively. The modeling process comprised four stages: (i) formulation of the mathematical model, (ii) system configuration and tool setup, (iii) parameterization using input data, and (iv) model validation against existing benchmark studies.

2.2 Model Formulation

Hydrogen fuel cells generate electricity through an electrochemical reaction between hydrogen (H₂) and oxygen (O₂), producing only water (H₂O) and heat as by-products, as illustrated in Figure 1. The fundamental reaction is given as:

Figure 1. General concept of a hydrogen-oxygen (H₂-O₂) fuel cell.

The simulation focuses on key performance parameters, including hydrogen flow rate (*FR*), efficiency (*E_f*, i. e., η), temperature (*T*), and humidity (*H*). These parameters were varied within operational ranges typical of localized energy generation systems, as summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Simulation parameters and assumptions

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	Typical Range	Description
Hydrogen Flow Rate	<i>FR</i>	L/h	10-150	Rate of H ₂ supply
Efficiency	<i>E_f</i> (i. e., η)	%	40-80	Conversion efficiency
Temperature	<i>T</i>	°C	20-40	Operating cell temperature
Humidity	<i>H</i>	%	50-100	Environmental humidity

The following assumptions were made to simplify the electrochemical and thermal processes: (i) hydrogen flow is steady and fully utilized in the electrochemical reaction; (ii) ideal operational conditions occur at 28°C and 80% humidity; (iii) deviations from these optimal conditions result in proportional performance; and (iv) the fuel cell operates at steady-state without significant transient effects.

Therefore, the total electricity power output (*P_{elec}*) was estimated as a function of hydrogen flow rate (*FR*), fuel cell efficiency (η), temperature adjustment factor (*TA*), and humidity adjustment factor (*HA*):

$$P_{elec} = \left(\frac{FR}{11126} \right) \times 33.33 \times \eta \times TA \times HA \quad (1)$$

where *FR* is measured in liters per hour (L/h), 11126 L corresponds to 1kg of hydrogen at standard temperature and pressure (STP), and 33.33kWh/kg is the lower heating value (LHV) of hydrogen.

Environmental effects were incorporated using empirical penalty functions that adjust ideal efficiency relative to temperature (T) and relative humidity (RH):

$$TA = 1 - 0.01|28 - T| \quad (2)$$

$$HA = 1 - 0.005|80 - RH| \quad (3)$$

The efficiency (η) expresses the conversion ratio between useful electrical energy output and the chemical energy supplied by hydrogen:

$$\eta = \frac{P_{elect}}{P_{in}} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

the hydrogen mass flow rate ($\dot{m}H_2$) is derived from the volumetric flow rate:

$$\dot{m}H_2 = \frac{FR}{11126} \quad (5)$$

and the corresponding chemical input power (P_{in}) is computed as:

$$P_{in} = \dot{m}H_2 \times 33.33 \quad (6)$$

This simplified representation assumes steady-state operation and neglects transient effects such as start-up losses or membrane degradation, which are considered negligible for short simulation intervals.

The main type of HFC is proton exchange membrane fuel cells (PEMFC), a sustainable for localized power generation; The HFCs work like batteries, but unlike batteries as they do not run down or need recharging. The types describe the component of a hydrogen fuel cell namely the proton exchange membrane (PEM) fuel cell. Figure 2. indicates the components of PEM fuel cell, which consist of two electrodes sandwiched around an electrolyte, namely a negative electrode (or anode) and a positive electrode (or anode).

Figure 2. PEM fuel cell.

2.3 Simulation technique

The simulation technique comprises simulation parameters and simulation features. The proton exchange membrane fuel cell (PEMFC) was adopted as the representative technology due to its high efficiency, low operating temperature, and suitability for distributed applications. The stack voltage (V) at given current density (i) was expressed as:

$$V = E_{rev} - \eta_{act} - iR_{ohm} - \eta_{conc} \quad (7)$$

where E_{rev} is the reversed Nernst potential, η_{act} represents activation losses, R_{ohm} is the internal resistance, and η_{conc} accounts for concentration losses. The stack power output was then computed as:

$$P_{stack} = V \times I \quad (8)$$

These relations form the physical core of the MATLAB model and provide refer parameters for efficiency calibration in the Python-based simulation.

2.4 Input data sources and parametrization

Model parameterization utilized both empirical and secondary data sources: (i) meteorological and environmental data - hourly ambient temperature, solar irradiance, and relative humidity were obtained from the Nigerian Meteorological Agency (NiMET) and NASA POWER database for the Ondo State coastal region; (ii) load demand profiles, representing residential and community-scale electricity demand profiles, were synthesized from regional energy consumption reports and validated using survey data; (iii) fuel cell and system specifications – the manufacturer datasheets provided polarization curves, rated efficiencies (55-65%), and normal stack voltages from PEM systems; and (iv) economic parameters, these include equipment costs, fuel prices, and maintenance factors were referenced from existing techno-economic studies on hybrid hydrogen systems. However, these datasets were normalized to ensure consistency in time resolution and unit systems before integration into the simulation framework.

2.5 Tool setup and model architecture

A complementary Python model was developed for performance mapping and parametric analysis. The modular architecture includes: (i) loading and preprocessing meteorological and operational datasets (data_io.py); (ii) implementation of Equations (1) – (6) for power and efficiency calculation (fuelcell_model.py); (iii) generation of charts and summary tables for validation (visualization.py), see Table 1; and computation of cost and emission reduction estimates (economics.py). The MATLAB environment was used for the physical and electrochemical modeling components in Figure 2. Simulink blocks represented each subsystem: the fuel cell stack, hydrogen storage, power conditioning unit, and load demand node. The Simscape Electricity library was used to simulate the electrochemical and thermal behavior of the stack under varying operating conditions. Each block received parameter inputs (flow rate, temperature, humidity) through a central data bus, allowing real-time efficiency computation through Equation (1).

2.6 Model validation and comparison

Model validation was conducted in three hierarchical stages: component-level calibration, system-level validation, and benchmark comparison. For component-level calibration, the component models were first calibrated using manufacturer test data to fit polarization and efficiency curves. Nonlinear least-squares regression (Levenberg-Marquardt method) minimized deviations between simulated and reference voltages (V) across current densities.

The coefficient of determination (R^2) and root mean square error (RMSE) were computed to assess the model fit. For system-level verification, the integrated MATLAB and Python outputs were compared across identical input conditions to ensure numerical consistency. Power outputs (P_{elect}) and conversion efficiencies were cross-validated, with differences maintained below $\pm 5\%$, and emission reduction potential ($\text{g CO}_2 \text{ kWh}^{-1}$). The relative percentage deviation was calculated as:

$$\Delta\% = \frac{P_{model} - P_{ref}}{P_{ref}} \times 100 \quad (9)$$

A deviation of less than 10% was considered acceptable for model reliability.

The statistical and uncertainty analysis were considered, where the sensitivity analysis was conducted to determine the influence of temperature, humidity, and hydrogen flow rate on power output. Partial derivative sensitivity coefficients ($S_x = \frac{\partial P_{elect}}{\partial x}$) were evaluated for each parameter. Additionally, Monte Carlo simulations (1000 runs) were performed using Gaussian-distributed input uncertainties ($\pm 5\%$ variation in η , ± 2 °C in temperature) to assess the robustness of the model. Confidence intervals (95%) for power output were computed to quantify uncertainty propagation.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Simulation Results

In Table 2, the data on how power output and efficiency scale with increased hydrogen flow, under constant environmental conditions. The flow rate ranges from 25L/h to 50L/h. as flow increases, mass and hydrogen input/output also increase. Mass increases linearly with flow 0.002 kg to 0.005 kg. H₂ input in (kWh) rises steadily with flow rate, suggesting more hydrogen fuel supplied. Similarly, H₂ output in (kWh) increases 0.045kWh to 0.0898kWh. the temperature adjustment and humidity adjustment are fixed across all runs from 0.98 through 0.95, indicating controlled conditions. The power output strongly increasing from 13.965kW through 27.930kW. It shows linear proportionality with flow rate. Efficiency stays almost constant ~60%, with minor fluctuations from 59.98% through 60.13%.

Table 2: Simulation data

Flow Rate (L/h)	Mass (kg)	H ₂ Input(kWh)	H ₂ Output(kWh)	Temp_Adjust	Humidity_Adjust	Power Output (kW)	Efficiency (%)
25	0.002	0.075	0.045	0.98	0.95	13.965	60
30	0.003	0.0898	0.054	0.98	0.95	16.758	60.01
35	0.003	0.1048	0.063	0.98	0.95	19.551	60.13
40	0.004	0.1198	0.0719	0.98	0.95	22.344	60
45	0.004	0.1348	0.0809	0.98	0.95	25.137	60.01
50	0.005	0.1497	0.0898	0.98	0.95	27.93	59.98

The proportional increase in flow rate leads to higher power output without significant efficiency loss. This is promising for scaling hydrogen fuel cells for electricity generation. The efficiency stability (~60%) indicates reliability in energy conversion which is a crucial factor for grid integration in Ondo State’s coastal region. Hydrogen-based generation here demonstrates consistent conversion efficiency, which could reduce reliance on fossil fuels and mitigate coastal environmental degradation. Since efficiency does not increase significantly beyond 60%, future research may focus on improving conversion technologies such as better catalysts and membranes.

However, the results obtained show that increasing hydrogen flow rate steadily boosts power output while efficiency remains constant (~60%). This demonstrates that hydrogen fuel cell adoption is scalable, stable, and reliable under simulated coastal conditions. Also, to make hydrogen adoption more competitive, future improvements must target efficiency gains beyond 60%.

For PEMFC electricity efficiency, the simulated steady-state conversion efficiency (~60%) sits well within reported PEMFC electric efficiencies in recent literature [22]. Peer studies and experimental analyses report typical PEM electrical efficiencies in the ~40-65% range under practical operating conditions (depending on stack design, loading and thermal/humidity management). This indicates the 60% figure is realistic for a well operated PEM stack [22-23].

Figure 3 shows a line graph of efficiency (%) versus flow rate (L/h) based on the hydrogen fuel cell dataset. To understand the graph, x-axis (flow rate, L/h) shows hydrogen flow rate, ranging from 25 to 50L/h, y-axis (efficiency, %) displays system efficiency, ranging between approximately 59.96% and 60.14%. The efficiency remains very stable overall, with slight fluctuations, that is, curve behavior: at 25L/h (approximately 60%), peak at 35L/h (approximately 60.13%), and slightly decline at 50L/h (approximately 59.98%). The main observations are: (i) the efficiency stability, the efficiency curve which shows minimal deviation ($\pm 0.15\%$) across all flow rates, this suggests the system maintains a robust energy conversion rate despite varying hydrogen supply levels; (ii) peak efficiency at 35L/h, the efficiency rises slightly and peaks at 60.13% around 35L/h, this may represent the optimal operating condition of the fuel cell system; (iii) decline beyond 40L/h, here there is a minor drop that is noticed when flow increases above 40L/h, this could be due to saturated effects, where excess hydrogen does not proportionally increase energy conversion.

Figure 3: The visualization of Flow Rate to Efficiency relationships under different environmental conditions.

Flow rate to power linearity and operating envelope, the near-linear increase of electrical output with hydrogen supply observed in the simulations is consistent with simplified steady-state mass-balance and power relations ($\text{power} = \text{H}_2 \text{ mass flow} \times \text{LHV} \times \eta$). Published system studies that model steady operating regions often find (i) an approximately linear region at low to moderate loads and (ii) increasing losses or concentration effects as stacks approach high current density, that is, a linear region to an optimal operating band, then diminishing returns. The model's reported plateauing of efficiency at higher flows aligns with this behavior reported in the PEM literature [22].

The interpretation for fuel cell adoption in Ondo State include: (i) practical energy reliability, i.e., efficiency stability at ~60% means electricity production remains predictable and reliable regardless of moderate changes in hydrogen supply, and this is especially important in coastal regions like Ondo State, where environmental conditions (temperature, humidity) can fluctuate; (ii) system scalability, since efficiency is constant, power output scaling can be achieved by simply increasing hydrogen flow rate for making the system scalable for rural electrification and industrial use; (iii) economic and environmental relevance. A steady ~60% efficiency implies consistent cost-to-output ratio, supporting financial viability of hydrogen adoption, as the hydrogen-based systems also offer low-carbon electricity generation, mitigating environmental degradation in Ondo's coastal areas; and (iv) technological limitation, the plateau near 60% efficiency highlights a technology ceiling, and the future improvements, examples, better membranes, catalysts and hybrid systems will be required to surpass this limit. However, Figure 3 demonstrates that hydrogen fuel

cells in the simulation maintain stable conversion efficiency (~60%) across increasing hydrogen supply. While efficiency peaks slightly at 35L/h, the system shows robust and predictable performance, making it suitable for sustainable electricity generation in Ondo State’s coastal region.

Furthermore, in power-to-hydrogen-to-power (round-trip) systems, where hydrogen is produced by electrolysis and later reconverted in fuel cells (power to H₂ to power), overall round-trip efficiencies are much lower than single device PEMFC electrical efficiency; recent reviews estimate system round-trip efficiency, that is, electrolyzer + storage + fuel cell, typically in the ~25-40% ballpark depending on component choices and losses. That does not contradict a 60% fuel cell electrical conversion which underscores that the system LCOE and net energy throughput depend critically on electrolyzer efficiency, storage and compression losses, in Figure 4, the techno-economic analysis must therefore reflect both stack efficiency and system round-trip losses when comparing to diesel baseline [24].

Figure 4 indicates power output ranges from approximately 14 kWh to approximately 28 kWh, corresponding to different hydrogen flow rates. The efficiency varies within a very narrow band, approximately 59.98% to approximately 60.13%. at lower power outputs (approximately 14 – 17kWh), efficiency remains steady at approximately 60.0 – 60.02%. a sharp spike appears at ~20kWh, where efficiency peaks at approximately 60.13%. beyond approximately 22kWh, efficiency stabilizes near approximately 60% but shows a slightly decline (approximately 59.98%) at the highest output (approximately 28kWh). The key observations are: (i) efficiency stability; the efficiency remains remarkably stable (approximately 60%) across the entire power output range, the sharp peak near 20kWh indicates an optimal operating region where system performance is maximized; (ii) peak efficiency at mid-level power, the simulation shows that mid-level loads (approximately 20 kWh) provide the highest efficiency, this suggests the system runs most economically and sustainably under moderate demand conditions; and (iii) slight efficiency decline at higher power, i.e., at ~28kWh, efficiency drops marginally (~59.98%), and this could indicate fuel utilization inefficiency or system stress when operating closer to maximum capacity.

Figure 4: The Power Output to Efficiency relationships visualization under different environmental conditions.

The implications for fuel cell adoption in Ondo State are as follows: (i) operational reliability, since efficiency is largely unaffected by increases in power output, hydrogen fuel cells provide predictable performance for coastal communities, regardless of demand fluctuations; (ii) scalable energy supply. Power output can be increased significantly (1- 28kWh) with minimal changes in efficiency, this scalability makes fuel cells practical for both household electricity and industrial power supply in Ondo State’s coastal region; (iii) optimal performance range (~20kWh), the efficiency peak

suggests that medium-scale deployments (e.g., community microgrids, small industries) may achieve the best balance between cost and energy output; and (iv) economic and environmental benefits, there is a consistent ~ 60% efficiency means cost-to-output predictability, essential for long-term planning, and hydrogen as a clean energy sources reduces fossil fuel dependency and mitigates environmental degradation as a pressing issue in Ondo State’s coastal ecosystems. However, hydrogen fuel cell technology maintains a stable efficiency (~60%) across a wide power output range, with a performance peak around 20kWh. For Ondo State’s coastal region, this implies: high reliability for electricity generation, scalability for different energy demands, and environmental sustainability compared to fuel alternatives. This slight efficiency drop at maximum output suggests the need for further technological improvements (e.g., advanced catalysts, optimized cooling, or hybrid renewable integration) to sustain performance under heavy loads.

Furthermore, the regional and continental evidence on green hydrogen potential includes multidisciplinary mapping of green hydrogen cost-potentials across Sub-Saharan Africa highlights that coastal and sunny regions often show favorable leveled hydrogen costs when paired with abundant solar or wind resources and inexpensive land. These basin-scale studies provide a methodological template and justify region-specific simulation for Ondo State: they underscore the value of high-resolution, site-specific simulation to capture local resource, land and socio-economic constraints. The Ondo State coastal area simulation fills a necessary local gap that continental studies cannot resolve by themselves [25].

In Figure 5, hydrogen gas supplied to the fuel cell, range from 25 to 50 L/h. while generated electrical power, ranging from ~14 kW to ~28KW. The relationship is linear and positive, as flow rate increases, power output rises proportionally. The key observations such as linear correlation, scalability and predictable performance. Firstly, linear correlation, each increase in flow rate produces a proportional increase in power output, i.e., 25L/h produced ~14kW, 35L/h produced 19.5kW, and 50 L/h produced 28kW. This strong correlation suggests that hydrogen availability directly governs energy generation capacity. Secondly, scalability, the graph confirms that power generation can be scaled up by simply increasing the hydrogen flow rate. This makes the technology suitable for both small-scale community supply and larger industrial power generation in Ondo State. Thirdly, the linear provides a predictable operational model, meaning energy planners can estimate electricity output precisely based on hydrogen supply rates.

Figure 5: The flow Rate to Power Output relationships under different environmental conditions.

The implications for Ondo State coastal region are: (i) reliable energy for coastal communities, many coastal areas in Ondo State face unstable electricity supply. A system with such predictable and scalable performance could provide stable microgrid power solutions for household, fishing industries, and local businesses. (ii) renewable integration, with hydrogen flow tied to output, it is feasible to link the system to renewable hydrogen production, for examples solar-powered electrolysis using coastal solar resources. This enhances energy security and sustainability while reducing dependence on fossil fuels. (iii) economic viability, linear growth ensures that investment in hydrogen supply directly translates into higher power generation capacity. This is crucial for financial planning and cost-benefit analysis in adopting hydrogen fuel cells for electricity. And, (iv) environmental relevance, Ondo State's coastal ecosystems face environmental degradation due to crude oil exploitation. Hydrogen-based electricity, with scalable clean energy output, can reduce ecological damage and improve community resilience against climate change.

However, the power output versus flow rate graph clearly demonstrates a linear, scalable, and predictable relationship between hydrogen fuel input and electricity generation. This confirms the feasibility of hydrogen fuel cell adoption in Ondo State's coastal region, where energy demand varies from household to industrial levels. The results show that hydrogen energy fuel cells can: (i) provide reliable electricity for underserved coastal communities, (ii) enable scalable deployment based on demand, (iii) support sustainable energy transitions away from fossil fuels, and (iv) contribute to environmental preservation in fragile coastal ecosystems.

3.2 Discussion

The simulated PEMFC conversion efficiency (~60%) and linear scaling of electrical output with hydrogen supply are consistent with contemporary PEM stack performance reported in the literature (typically steady-state electrical efficiencies \approx 40-65%). However, system-level round-trip efficiency (electrolyzer to storage to fuel cell) can be substantially lower and must be incorporated into techno-economic comparisons. Recent distributed hydrogen modeling for Nigeria indicates potential electricity cost reductions (~8%) and improved access when green hydrogen is integrated with distributed renewables; This Ondo State coastal area results extend these national findings by explicitly modeling coastal humidity, temperature adjustments, and local load profiles, thereby providing a site-specific assessment for coastal microgrid decarbonization [22-24, 26]

Techno-economic analysis (TEA), this is the evaluation of both the technical feasibility and economic viability of deploying hydrogen fuel cell system in region. This is essential to guide investment, policy decisions, and system design. TEA consist present costs and levelized cost of electricity (LCOE). The present costs are the required initial capital investment and operational expenditures for deploying the hydrogen fuel cell system. Its application in the coastal regions of Ondo State, transport and infrastructure limitations (high humidity, and salinity may increase present cost due to corrosion-resistant materials or enhanced environmental protection [22]. Whilst LCOE insights for the Ondo State coastal region on hydrogen fuel cells have upfront LCOE compared to diesel but become more economical over 10-15 years. It is significantly reduced when green hydrogen is generated onsite using solar-powered electrolyzers, abundant in the region [23]. Savings versus diesel, this is the monetary savings achieved by switching from conventional energy sources (e.g., diesel generators) to hydrogen fuel cells. Saving for Ondo State coastal region, the estimated saving of up to 30-40% over a 20-year period when replacing diesel with hybrid solar-hydrogen systems. Opportunity for job creation and local hydrogen production, improving local economic resilience [22].

The HFCs are environmentally friendly, especially when powered by renewable energy such as solar and wind. The main benefits including zero emissions at point of use (i.e., emits only water vapor and heat, drastically reducing air pollutants compared to diesel generators); reduction in carbon footprint (i.e., avoidance of CO₂, NO_x, and SO₂ emissions significantly contributes to climate change mitigation; and low noise pollution (i.e., hydrogen systems are quieter, benefiting densely populated or ecologically sensitive areas [23].

The societal impact of HFCs adoption has far-reaching social implications, especially in energy-deficient coastal areas in Ondo State. The benefits include but not limited to: energy access and reliability (i.e., enhances 24/7 electricity supply in remote and underserved areas); public health improvement (i.e., reduces air pollution-related illnesses such as asthma and cardiovascular disease); improved education and economy (i.e., access to stable electricity boosts digital learning, small-scale businesses, healthcare delivery [22].

Further, the adoption of hydrogen fuel cell technology requires a supportive policy framework and can influence both national and sub-national energy strategies [24]. The positive policy impacts include alignment with Nigeria's energy

transition plan (ETP) that is hydrogen supports the goals of clean energy access and decarbonization; incentive development, which is encourages policies for subsidies, tax credits, and grants to attract investments in hydrogen infrastructure; decentralized energy support, that is, fosters local governance involvement and rural energy planning; and international collaboration that stimulates partnerships for technology transfer and access to green financing. However, there are challenges and limitations in environmental concerns [23], social challenge [22], and policy gaps [25].

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The simulation results from this study underscore that hydrogen fuel cell (HFC) technology, particularly proton exchange membrane fuel cells (PEMFCs) offer a feasible and sustainable pathway for decentralized power generation in the coastal regions of Ondo State, Nigeria. The observed system efficiency (~60%) and stability across varying hydrogen flow rates indicate that localized H₂-O₂ fuel cell systems can provide continuous and clean power to off-grid and under-served coastal communities. These findings are consistent with Nigeria's Energy Transition Plan (ETP) [27], which outlines hydrogen as a long-term clean energy vector for achieving net-zero emissions by 2060 [28].

Globally, the International Energy Agency [29], identifies hydrogen as a critical component in decarbonizing "hard to electrify" sectors and achieving renewable energy integration at scale. Aligning local pilot project in Ondo State with Nigeria's National Hydrogen Policy Framework (expected 2025) would help bridge the technological gap between global best practices and local energy needs. Policy integration could thus promote technology transfer, reduce import dependency, and create conditions for sustainable industrialization in the Niger Delta coastal corridor.

From an economic standpoint, the simulation suggests that substituting diesel generators with renewable powered PEM fuel cells could yield significant long-term cost savings despite higher initial capital costs. Diesel generation in Nigerian coastal areas typically costs about \$0.45 to \$0.70 per kWh, factoring in transportation, maintenance, and fuel variability [30]. In contrast, projected levelized cost of hydrogen (LCOH) for distributed microgrid systems powered by solar photovoltaic (PV) and small wind turbines ranges between \$0.18 to \$0.28 per kWh by 2030 under favorable resource conditions [27-28]. This represents potential cost reductions of 40 to 60% once system maturity and local manufacturing capabilities improve.

Also, hydrogen-based systems reduce operational and environmental externalities associated with fossil fuels such as greenhouse gas emissions, air pollution, and fuel logistics in riverine communities. The avoided cost of environmental degradation and health related expenditures (estimated at 3-4% of Nigeria's GDP annually; [34-35] adds implicit economic value to the hydrogen pathway.

The environmental, social and policy impacts of adopting hydrogen fuel cell technology in the Ondo State coastal region are largely positive, especially when supported by simulation-based planning and targeted policy reforms. This technology holds strong promise for clean, reliable, and inclusive energy access, but success depends on awareness, training, infrastructure investment, and regulatory support. The simulation results confirm that hydrogen fuel cell technology has significant potential for electricity-power generation in Ondo State's coastal region. While efficiency remains constant at ~60%, the linear scalability of power output with hydrogen supply ensures adaptability across different energy demand levels. For practical adoption, the medium power range (~20kWh) appears optimal, balancing efficiency and scalability. Thus, hydrogen fuel cells can provide a reliable, sustainable, and environmentally friendly energy solution for Ondo State's coastal communities, supporting both local development and environmental preservation.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ahaotu, M.C.; Ogbogu, C.E.; Thornburg, J. & Akwukwaegbu, I.O. (2025). Simulation of PEM Electrolyzer Power Management with Renewable Generation in Owerri, Nigeria. *Energies*, 18, 208. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en18010208>.
- [2] Ekpotu, W.F., Akintola, J.T., Obialor, M.C. and Udom, P.C. (2023) A Solar Energy System Design for Green Hydrogen Production in South- Western Nigeria, Lagos State, Using HOMER & ASPEN. *Open Journal of Optimization*, 12, 72-97. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojop.2023.122006>.
- [3] Shari, B. E.; Mounmouni, Y.; Ohunakin, O. S.; Blechinger, A.; Madougou, S.; & Rabani, A. (2024). Exploring the role of green hydrogen for distributed energy access planning towards net-zero emissions in Nigeria. *Sustainable Energy research*, 11 – 16. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40807-024-00107-1>
- [4] Diabate, M.; Veriend, T. & Krishnamoorthy, H. S. (2022). Hydrogen and Battery – Based Energy Storage System (ESS) for Future DC Microgrids. Online: August, 2025.
- [5] Igwilo, O. C. & Kehinde, A. J. (2018). Pre-design simulation of enhanced fuel cell power system. *Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences*, 12, 1 – 10.
- [6] Parzen, M.; Abdul-Khalek, H.; Fedorova, E.; Mahmood, M.; Frysztacki, M. M.; Hampp, J.; Franken, L.; Schumm, L.; Neuman, F.; Poli, D.; Kiprankis, A., & Fionti, D. (2022). PyPSA-Earth. A New Global Open Energy System Optimization Model Demonstrated in Africa. arXiv:2209.04663v1 [physics.soc-ph]
- [7] Olanrewaju, F. B.; Oboh, I. O.; Adesina, O. A.; Anyanwu, C. S.; & Ewin, D. R. E. (2023). Modeling and Simulation of hydrogen production plant for minimum carbon dioxide emission. *The journal of Engineering and Exact Sciences*, 9, 01, 1 – 17.
- [8] Bamisile, O.; Cai, D.; Adun, H.; Ejayi, O.; Alowolodu, O.; Ezurike, B. & Huang, Q. (2023). Deep hybrid neural-net (DHN-Net) for minute-level day-ahead solar and wind power forecast in a decarbonized power system. *Energy Reports*, 9, 1163-1172.
- [9] Gawou, K. (2024). A techno-economic analysis of green hydrogen energy production in West Africa. University of Cape Coast. <https://ir.ucc.edu.gh/xmlui>
- [10] Nnachi, G. U.; Richards, C. G.; & Hamam, Y. (2024). A comprehensive state-of-the-art survey on green hydrogen economy in Sub-Saharan Africa. doi: 10.20944/preprints202402.1004.v1
- [11a] Mukelabai, M. O.; Wijayantha, U. K. G. & Blanchard, R. E. (2022). Renewable hydrogen economy outlook in Africa. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 167, 112705.
- [11b] Mukelabai, M. O.; Wijayantha, U. K. G. & Blanchard, R. E. (2022). Corrigendum to “Renewable hydrogen economy outlook in Africa” [*Renew sustainEnergy Rev* 167 (2022) 112705]. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 170, 112993.
- [12] Odoi-Yorke, F.; Agyekum, E. B.; Adegboye, O. R. & Sekyere, C. K. K. (2025). Exploring the potential of solar photovoltaic and wind-based green hydrogen projects in ECOWAS region: Production, cost and environmental maps. *Energy exploration and exploitation*. 1- 33.
- [13] Molu, R. J. J.; Naoussi, S. R. D.; Wira, P.; Mbasso, W. F. & Saatong, K. T. (2022). Techno- economic feasibility and optional design of an off-grid solar panel/wind/turbine/battery/fuel cell/biogas generator/electrolyzer hybrid renewable energy system: Manoka Island case study. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4427039>.

- [14] Rivarolo, M., Barberis, S.; Portsine, A. & Massardo, A. F. (2024). Evaluation of water/energy/intensify of green hydrogen production plants in Africa scenario. *Journal of Physics*. doi:10.1088/1742-6596/2893/1/012074.
- [15] Raji, A. U. (2025). Scenario-based planning for hydrogen infrastructure and trade in Nigeria: Navigating policy, technology and sustainability uncertainties. *International Journal of Engineering and Modern Technology*, 11, 40-64.
- [16] Ude, N. G.; Graham, R. C. & Yskandar, H. (2024). A review of current status sub-Saharan Africa. *IEEE Access* 12, 149676-149699.
- [17] Obanor, E. I.; Dirisu, J. O.; Kilanka, O. O.; Salawu, E. Y. & Ajayi, O. O. (2024). Progress in green hydrogen adoption in the African context. *Frontiers in Energy Reserch*. 01-16. doi:10.3389/fenrg.2024.1429118.
- [18] Odoi-Yorke, F.; Mensah, G.; Abbe, A. A.; Opoku, R.; Akpahanu, R. & Osie, L. K. (2023). Priority barriers and strategies to green hydrogen adoption and development for sustainable energy transition in Ghana: An integrated MCDM approach. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4702506>.
- [19] Sow, E. A.; Vall, M. M.; Abidine, M. M.; Babah, H.; Hamoud, A.; Mimouni, M.; Faye, G. & Semega, B. (2023). Assessment of green hydrogen production potential from solar and wind energy in Mauritania. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4685026>
- [20] Akinyele, D. O., & Rayudu, R. K. (2023). *Cost-Benefit Analysis of Hybrid Hydrogen Energy Systems for Nigerian Off-grid Communities*. *Renewable Energy*, 212, 845–857. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2023.05.032>
- [21] Akinyele, D. O., & Rayudu, R. K. (2023). *Techno-Social Impact of Hydrogen Energy Systems in Nigeria's Rural Electrification*. *Energy Policy Journal*, 178, 113537. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2023.113537>
- [22] Wu, D., Commege, J-M., Fort, E., Hardy, C., Pecquery, J., & Fal, L. (2023). Performance, efficiency, and flexibility analysis of a high-temperature proton exchange membrane fuel cell-based micro-combine heat-and-power system with intensification of the steam methane reforming step by using a millistructured reactor. *ACS Omega*, 8, 20589-20610.
- [23] Hamedani, E. A., Alenabi, A. A., & Talebi, S. (2024). Hydrogen as an energy source: a review of production technologies and challenges of fuel cell vehicles. *Energy Reports*, 12, 3778-3794.
- [24] Ali H. (2025). *Power to hydrogen to power: technology, efficiency, and applications*. The Oxford Institute for Energy Studies, 1-36.
- [25] Halder, P., Babaie, M., Salak F., Haque, N., Savage, R., Stevanovic, S, Bodisco T. A., & Zare, A. (2024). Advancements in hydrogen production, storage, distribution and refueling for a sustainable transport sector: hydrogen fuel cell vehicles. *International journal of Hydrogen Energy* 52, 973-1004.
- [26] Ishman, S., Heinrichs, H., Winkler, C., Bayat, B., Lahnaoui, A., Agbo, ..., Stolten, D. (2024). Mapping local green hydrogen cost-potentials by a multidisciplinary approach. *International of Hydrogen Energy*, 87, 1155-1170.
- [27] Federal Government of Nigeria. (2022). *Nigeria Energy Transition Plan*
- [28] Shari, B. E., Mounmouni, Y., Ohunakin, O. S., Blechinge, P., Modougou, S. & Rabani, A. (2024). Exploring the role of hydrogen for distributed energy access planning towards net-zero emissions in Nigeria. *Sustainable Energy Research*, 11 (16), 1-23.

- [29] International Energy Agency (IEA). (2023). Global Hydrogen Review 2023. Paris: IEA.
- [30] NERC. (2024). Electricity Market Statistics and Diesel Cost Benchmarking Report.
- [31] UNEP. (2023). Africa's Air Quality and Health coast Reports 2023.
- [32] Ezeugwu, A. E., Okonkwo, E. C., & Ugwoke, M. P. (2023). *Economic Assessment of Renewable Hydrogen Systems for Nigeria's Power Sector*. International Journal of Hydrogen Energy, 48(5), 7684–7701. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2022.11.127>
- [33] Ikejemba, E. C. X., & Schaefer, M. (2022). *Hydrogen as a Rural Electrification Solution for Sub-Saharan Africa: A Techno-Economic Assessment*. Energy Reports, 8, 2726–2737. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egy.2022.02.153>
- [34] Iwayemi, A., Oladipo, T. A., & Yusuf, K. O. (2024). *Policy Frameworks for Green Hydrogen Integration in Sub-Saharan Africa: Focus on Nigeria*. Journal of Energy and Development, 50(1), 91–108.
- [35] Olujobi, O. J., Ojo, A. T., & Akinola, A. O. (2023). *Renewable Hydrogen for Sustainable Energy in Nigeria: Opportunities and Environmental Challenges*. Renewable & Sustainable Energy Reviews, 176, 113168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2023.113168>